

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

TRANSPORT-RELATED FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF GEO-ECOLOGICAL MONITORING OF LAND RESTORATION FOR TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of this research topic stems from the fact that transport infrastructure underpins the functioning of regions and the state, and creates opportunities for efficient connections and the development of the logistics system. Transport infrastructure is of particular importance in countering the consequences of aggressive actions.

To resolve complex issues, there is a need to establish a quantitative basis for effective decision-making within the system of geo-ecological monitoring of the restoration of transport infrastructure land. In this regard, a key issue is the identification and application of transport factors to form a multi-level system of indicators for geo-ecological monitoring.

The research objective regarding the identification of transport factors for the formation and use of geo-ecological monitoring of the restoration of transport infrastructure land has been achieved.

As a result of the study, the significance of transport factors in geo-ecological monitoring of transport infrastructure land restoration has been substantiated and these factors have been identified. This has enabled the formation of a basis for the development and application of a system to assess the level of implementation of geo-ecological monitoring and has laid the groundwork for effective decision-making within the transport infrastructure land restoration system.

Keywords: transport factors, land restoration, geo-ecological monitoring, transport infrastructure, geographic information systems, factors, assessment system.

Introduction. Transport infrastructure underpins the functioning of regions and the state, creating opportunities for efficient connections and shaping the logistics system. Transport infrastructure is of particular importance in countering the consequences of aggressive

actions. At the same time, issues arise regarding the effectiveness of transport infrastructure operations.

The freight turnover change index for the period under review is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Freight turnover index for the period under review, relative units [1]

The values of this indicator also reveal a fluctuating nature of changes and ambiguous trends. The lowest freight turnover in recent years was observed in 2022, when it fell by almost half.

The freight turnover change index by mode of transport for the period under review is shown in Fig. 2. It was found that freight turnover increased in 2021 for rail, road, water and air transport. Only the volume of freight turnover by air transport decreased.

Fig. 2. Index of changes in freight turnover by mode of transport for the period under review, relative units [1]

No data is available for 2022 due to the outbreak of active hostilities. In 2024, freight volumes are increasing for rail and road transport, whilst volumes for

water transport are declining. No data is available on freight volumes for pipeline and air transport.

The index of changes in passenger traffic for the period under review is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Passenger traffic change index for the period under review, relative units [1]

A wave-like pattern in passenger traffic was also observed over the period under review, with the lowest figures recorded in 2022. The consequences of the aggression include a decline in land-use efficiency and in

the potential for the implementation and operation of modern geoinformation systems.

To ensure the efficient functioning of transport infrastructure, conditions are being created for the allocation and use of land, and the establishment of spatial planning. Of particular importance are modern monitoring tools, which involve the use of geoinformation systems.

The transport system has a complex structure and requires investment resources. To facilitate the attraction and utilization of domestic and foreign investment, a regulatory framework has been established: the Laws of Ukraine «On the Protection of Foreign Investments in Ukraine» of 10 September 1991 № 1540a-XII, «On Investment Activity» of 18 September 1991 № 1560-XII, «On the Elimination of Discrimination in the Taxation of Business Entities Established Using Property and Funds of Domestic Origin» №1457-III, «On Joint Investment Institutions (Mutual and Investment Funds)» № 2299-III, «On Amendments to Certain Laws of Ukraine Aimed at Eliminating Cases of Tax Evasion by Certain Enterprises Established with the Participation of Foreign Investors» dated 20 December 2001 № 2899-III.

Thus, to resolve the complex issues presented, there is a need to establish a quantitative basis for effective decision-making within the system of geo-ecological monitoring of the restoration of transport infrastructure land. In this regard, a key issue is the identification and application of transport factors to form a multi-level system of geo-ecological monitoring indicators.

Justification of existing theoretical approaches.

Theoretical principles regarding the identification of directions and characteristics of the development and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of the restoration of land used for transport infrastructure are presented in academic studies, with the focus limited to specific components. In particular, the functional areas of monitoring are defined in [2, 3]. Geographic Information Systems (GIS), which are described in [4, 5]. The development and implementation of geo-ecological monitoring of the restoration of land used for transport infrastructure is carried out using artificial intelligence, surveying technology and other equipment designed to provide spatial data [6, 7].

Geo-ecological monitoring depends on the factors that influence its development. The importance of conducting a factor analysis and identifying the relevant factors is emphasised in the studies [8, 9].

At the same time, questions remain unresolved regarding the development and application of geo-ecological monitoring for the restoration of land used for transport infrastructure, taking into account the impact of transport-related factors.

The aim of the study is to identify the transport-related factors influencing the development and application of geo-ecological monitoring in the restoration of land used for transport infrastructure.

Main section. Key issues and the identification of transport-related factors within the geo-ecological monitoring system for the restoration of land used for transport infrastructure are presented in [10–12].

A selection has been made of local transport factors relating to the development and application of geo-

ecological monitoring for the restoration of land used for transport infrastructure:

- the level of interaction between public transport enterprises and government and local authorities ($RTIL_{31}^1$);
- the allocation and use of land for transport purposes ($RTIL_{32}^1$);
- transport safety ($RTIL_{33}^1$);
- the level of land use for rail transport ($RTIL_{34}^1$);
- the use of land for maritime transport ($RTIL_{35}^1$);
- land for inland waterway transport ($RTIL_{36}^1$);
- road transport and road infrastructure ($RTIL_{37}^1$);
- air transport ($RTIL_{38}^1$);
- urban electric transport ($RTIL_{39}^1$);
- forest strips and land used by transport enterprises ($RTIL_{310}^1$);
- level of mobilisation preparedness of rail transport ($RTIL_{311}^1$);
- effectiveness of stakeholder relations in the field of road traffic ($RTIL_{312}^1$);
- road safety and design ($RTIL_{313}^1$);
- index of changes in freight turnover by region ($RTIL_{314}^1$);
- index of changes in passenger turnover by region ($RTIL_{315}^1$);
- removal of existing barriers in the field of logistics and multimodal transport within national corridors ($RTIL_{316}^1$).

Conclusions. The study has demonstrated the significance of transport factors in the geo-ecological monitoring of transport infrastructure land rehabilitation and has identified these factors. This has provided a basis for the development and application of a system to assess the implementation of geo-ecological monitoring, and has laid the groundwork for effective decision-making in the field of transport infrastructure land rehabilitation.

References

1. Official website of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine. URL: <https://www.ukrstat.gov.ua>
2. Mamonov, K., Vatulia, G., Goi, V., & Nelin, E. (2025). Establishing a quantitative basis for the development and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure in regions. *Automobile roads and road construction*, 118(2), 116–123. http://publications.ntu.edu.ua/avtodorogi_i_stroitelstvo/118.2/116.pdf
3. Vatulia, G., Mamonov, K., Goi, V., & Nelin, E. (2025). Methods for establishing and implementing geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure in regions. *Scientific Bulletin of Construction*, 113, 216–221. <https://svc.kname.edu.ua/index.php/svc/uk/article/view/1920/1858>
4. Mamonov, K., Frolov, V., Kasyanov, V., & Yevdokimov, A. (2025). Geoinformation support for soil condition in the territorial organisation system. *Roads and road construction*, 118(2), 138–147.

http://publications.ntu.edu.ua/avtodorogi_i_stroitelstvo/118.2/138.pdf

5. Mamonov, K., Nesterenko, S., Pilicheva, M., Afanasiev, A., & Tsyhenko, A. (2024). Geospatial analysis of the territory for solving urban planning problems. *International Conference on Green Energy: Intelligent Transport Systems - Clean Energy Transitions (GreenEnergy 2023)*. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202450808021>

6. Voronkov, O., Nesterenko, S., & Kasyanov, V. (2022). Characteristics of assessing the accuracy of GPS surveying measurements. *Municipal Economy of Cities. Series: Technical Sciences and Architecture*, 3(170), 200–208. <https://doi.org/10.33042/2522-1809-2022-3-170-200-208>

7. Kravchuk, O., Nesterenko, S., & Kasyanov, V. (2024). Monitoring and administration of urban environment using geoinformation technologies. *Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift Für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, 83, 46–50. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12657254>

8. Mamonov, K., Shterndok, E., Viatkin, R. (2025). Urban planning support for land-use planning. *Automobile roads and road construction*, 117(2), 235–

241.

http://publications.ntu.edu.ua/avtodorogi_i_stroitelstvo/117.2/235.pdf

9. Mamonov, K., Kovalchuk, V., Goi, V., Mamonov, V. (2024). Urban planning factors influencing regional land use development. *Scientific Bulletin of Construction*, 111, 154–159. <https://svc.kname.edu.ua/index.php/svc/article/view/1804/1769>

10. Kudryantsev, V. (2022) Factors in the sustainable development of transport infrastructure. *Issues and Prospects for the Development of Entrepreneurship*, 29, 42–49. <https://doi.org/10.30977/PPB.2226-8820.2022.29.32>

11. Smerichevsky, S., Raicheva, L., & Mikhalchenko, O. (2022). Problems and prospects for the modernisation of the transport sector of the national economy. *Economy and Society*, (38). <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2022-38-76>

12. Dmytriyeva, O. (2019). Spatial inequality and sectoral-regional asymmetry in the innovative development of Ukraine's transport infrastructure. *Bulletin of Sumy National Agrarian University*, 3(81), 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.32845/bsnau.2019.3.9>